

(3, 7–16%). This is in accordance with the loss of HCN from M-1 peak in the case of 2-methylindole^{1a}. The ion 3 splits off acetylene molecule to give the ion 4 at m/e 77. Further, an ion (5) of m/e 130 (5.6–5.8%) is observed in the mass spectra of both 1 and 2. This ion obviously results from the parent ion by the loss of 2-aryl group. Ion 5 subsequently leads to the ion 6 at m/e 102 (10.6–12.4%). Our results indicate that in the case of 7-ethoxyindoles (3 and 4), the initial fragmentation occurs around the ethoxy group. Thus, the molecular ion 7 which forms the base peak, loses ethane or ethanol moieties to form the ions 8 and 9, respectively, at appropriate mass units. The ion 8 eliminates formyl radical, like phenols,

to form an ion at m/e 77. The molecular ion may also lose ethoxy radical to form the ion 11.

Benzindoles show a similar behaviour like indoles and the only appreciable fragmentation results by the loss of HCN from the parent ion which forms the base peak^{1a}. In the case of 2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1*H*-benz[*g*]indole (5) and 2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3*H*-benz[*e*]indole (6), the molecular

ions (12 and 13, respectively) lose $\text{N}\equiv\text{C}-$

to give the ion 14 at m/e 140. A peak at m/e 139 may be attributed to the ion 15 formed from the ion 14 by the loss of a hydrogen atom. This is in accordance with the results obtained in connection with the mass spectral studies of 2-carboxybenz[*e*]indole^{1a}. The ion 15 does not undergo further fragmentation as the fused ring systems are resistant to mass fragmentation. The mass spectra of these two benzindoles exhibited a peak at m/e 130.5 which corresponds to the doubly charged ion (Scheme 3)

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Reaction of 2-Hydroxydibenzoylmethanes with Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride in DMF-Water. Dielectric Constant Dependent Products: Isoxazole and Benzisoxazole

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ISOXAZOLE derivatives are well known as anti-bacterial¹, antitubercular², antiviral³, antifungal⁴, anticonvulsants⁵, and corrosion inhibitors for fuels and lubricants⁶. Lohiya⁷ in his recent work established that some of the previous workers had mistaken benzisoxazole derivative (it does not give ferric chloride colour due to absence of free phenolic OH group) as isoxazole. The benzisoxazole forms along with isoxazole (gives ferric chloride colour reaction) in DMF and aqueous DMF medium from 2-hydroxy-dibenzoylmethane derivative with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

The present investigation deals with the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride on some dibenzoylmethane derivatives (β -diketones) in DMF, DMF-water mixture and *N*-methylacetamide media; isolation of the products, isoxazole and benzisoxazole, and their formation ratio. An attempt has been made to explain the ratio of formation of

TABLE 1—ISOXAZOLE : BENZISOXAZOLE FORMATION

β-Diketone (M. p., °C)	Product (M. p., °C)	DMF Dielectric constant (36.7)	DMF—Water mixture (yield in mg)				N-Methyl acetamide Dielectric constant (140)
			9 : 1	8 : 2	7 : 3	6 : 4	
3a (134)	4a : 5a (150) (205)	750 : 300	360 : 550	320 : 680	250 : 930	140 : 850	200 : 950
3b (90)	4b-5b (106) (208)	1040 : 1	585 : 695	550 : 730	540 : 760	—	—
3c (115)	4c : 5c (106) (140)	435 : 625	450 : 710	480 : 820	280 : 850	190 : 970	—
3d (116)	4d : 5d (105) (226)	735 : 315	450 : 710	425 : 745	420 : 800	400 : 800	—

isoxazole and benzisoxazole on the basis of the dielectric constant of the medium of reaction.

3a-d with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in DMF, DMF-water (9 : 1, 7 : 3, 6 : 4) and N-methylacetamide gave the products as shown in Table 1. The formation of isoxazole (4a-d) and benzisoxazole (5a-d) depends on the medium of reaction. The pure DMF gave maximum amount of isoxazole while DMF-water mixture gave more of benzisoxazole with increasing amount of water in DMF-water mixture. When the ratio of DMF-water was 1 : 1, the reaction mixture was insoluble and hence no proper formation of the products were observed. The dielectric constant increases from pure DMF (36.7) to DMF-water mixture (<70) with increasing amount of water. Again when N-methylacetamide (dielectric constant 140) was used as a solvent, benzisoxazole was formed to the maximum extent. The increase in the yield of 5 is due to the increase in dielectric constant of the medium which suggests that the charge separation in the phenolic OH group is more favourable, and hence its active participation in the ring closure.

3

4

5

- a, R = CH₃, R' = OCH₃
- b, R = CH₃, R' = H
- c, R = H, R' = OCH₃
- d, R = R' = H

Experimental

2-Anisoyloxy-5-methylacetophenone : 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (obtained by Fries migration of *p*-cresylacetate) (0.1 mol, 15 g) and anisic acid (0.12 mol, 18.3 g) were dissolved in dry pyridine (60 ml). The solution was kept in cold water-bath and phosphorous oxychloride (0.07 mol, 7 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring and external cooling. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained below 40° throughout the addition of POCl₃. After 3 h the mixture was decomposed by cold 1 : 1 dilute HCl (till the solution was acidic to congo red paper), and the white product was filtered and washed with water and then with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove unreacted anisic acid. The solid was crystallised from rectified spirit to get 2-anisoyloxy-5-methylacetophenone (90%, 25 g), m.p. 115° (lit.⁹ 115°). Its alcoholic solution does not give colour reaction with ferric chloride solution.

Similarly, 2-benzoyloxy-5-methylacetophenone was prepared using benzoylchloride (Scotten-Bauhman reaction), m.p. 64° (lit.⁹ 64°). 2-Anisoyloxyacetophenone (m.p. 110°) and 2-benzoyloxyacetophenone (m.p. 82°) were prepared from 2-hydroxyacetophenone with anisic acid and with benzoic acid (or benzoylchloride), respectively.

2-Hydroxy 4'-methoxy-5-methyldibenzoylmethane (3a) : 2-Anisoyloxy-5-methylacetophenone (50 mmol, 14.2 g) was dissolved in dry pyridine (40 ml). The solution was warmed and was added to molten KOH (0.15 mol, 8.4 g) with stirring. The solution was stirred for 2 h and kept overnight. The product was decomposed by adding HCl (1 : 1) till the reaction mixture was acidic. Yellow solid was filtered, washed with 10% bicarbonate solution and then with water. The lemon-yellow product was crystallised from rectified spirit to get 2-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-5-methyldibenzoylmethane (3a; 80%, 11 g), m.p. 134° (lit.⁹ 134°) (Found : C, 71.5 ; H, 6.01. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ calcd. for : C, 71.8 ; H, 5.63%); alcoholic solution gave violet-blue colouration with neutral ferric chloride solution ; tlc R_f 1.0 in benzene/CCl₄ solvent ; ν_{max} 3 440 (OH), 1 620 (C=O), 1 260 (ArO), 1 030 (OCH₃) and 800 cm⁻¹ (C-H) ; λ_{max}

(CHCl₃) 235, 268, 288 and 382 nm; δ (CDCl₃ with TMS as internal standard) 2.34 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.8 (7H, m, ArH), 6.75 (1H, s, C-H), 11.96 (1H, s, O-H, 80%) and 4.56 (2H, s, CH₂, 20%); showed the keto-enol tautomerism in β -diketone (80%) enol and (20%) ketone.

Similarly 3b-d were prepared from the corresponding esters. Analysis was in accordance with the required molecular formula.

Reaction of 3a-d with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in DMF-water medium: 2-Hydroxy-4'-methoxy-5-methyldibenzoylmethane (3a; 5 mmol, 14 g) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (10 mmol, 0.7 g) were dissolved in DMF-water mixture. The solution was refluxed for 4 h, cooled and diluted with water. The gummy mass separated was washed several times with water and triturated with rectified spirit to get a white powder. It was boiled with carbon tetrachloride and insoluble product was separated to get 5a, m.p. 205° (Found: C, 70.0; H, 6.4. C₁₇H₁₆O₃N₂ calcd. for: C, 70.50; H, 6.84%); R_f 0.27 in benzene ν_{max} 3450 (OH), 3100 (NH), 1620 (C=N, C=C), 1310 (O-CH), 1260 (Ar-O ether), 1180 (C-O), 1040 (OCH₃), 980 (=N-O) and 800 cm⁻¹ (=C-H); λ_{max} 220, 269 and 313 nm; δ 1.56, 2.36, 3.90, 6.46, 6.8-8.0 (1H, s, OH; 3H, s, ArCH₃; 3H, s, OCH₃; 1H, s, NH; 8H, m, Ar-H; and olefinic =C-H).

The carbon tetrachloride solution on evaporation gave another product which was crystallised from rectified spirit to get 4a, m.p. 150° (Found: C, 72.32; H, 6.39. C₁₇H₁₅O₃N calcd. for: C, 72.6; H, 6.3%); ν_{max} 3210 (OH), 1630, 1620 (C=N, C=C), 1310 (OCH), 1265 (Ar-O ether), 1020 (O-CH₃), 950 (=N-O) and 790 cm⁻¹ (=C-H); δ 2.4, 3.94, 6.83, 6.90, 7.90 and 9.44 (3H, s, ArCH₃; 3H, s, OCH₃; 1H, s, heteroaromatic; 7H, m, Ar-H; 1H, s, O-H).

Similarly, 3b-d gave 4b-d and 5b-d (Table 1).

Reaction of 3a-d with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in DMF/N-methylacetamide: The reaction was carried out as above. 4a-d and 5a-d were isolated and the comparative yields tabulated. Only 3a was taken to study the reaction in N-methylacetamide.

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Triterpenoids and other Constituents of *Acacia tortilis* Wild.

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THE plant *Acacia tortilis* Wild. (Syn: *A. Radlana* Savi) and commonly known as Israeli babul (Leguminosae) was collected from the Northern semi-desert region of Rajasthan in January and was identified in the herbarium (No. 20292) Botany Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur. It was found to be very useful source of protein¹. The cellwall constituents, acid detergent fibres and cellulose found in the leaves provide as nutrients for the animals as fodders. Seeds contain organic matter and protein. Apigen-6,8-d-glucoside and rutin were isolated from the leaves². It was therefore, considered worth while to investigate the plant for its chemical compositions.

Stem-bark: Air-dried and finely chipped stem-bark of *A. tortilis* (4 kg) was exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and acetone, respectively. The petroleum ether extract concentrate (47 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh), being eluted with petroleum ether, benzene, ethyl acetate, and methanol mixtures of increasing polarity. The identity of the compounds obtained has been established from their physical properties (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) and in every case through the preparation of derivatives.

The petroleum ether extract gave (A) n-hexacosanol, m.p. 78° (lit³. 79°); acetate, m.p. 64° (lit³. 66°), (B) betulin, m.p. 250° (lit⁴. 251-52°); diacetate, m.p. 215-16° (lit⁵. 217°); dibenzoate, m.p. 178-79° (lit⁶. 182°), and (C) α -amyrin, m.p. 185-86° (lit⁷. 186°), acetate, m.p. 223° (lit⁸. 223-25°); benzoate, m.p. 193° (lit⁸. 193-94°).

The acetone extract gave (D) n-hexacosanol, m.p. 78° (lit³. 79°), acetate, m.p. 64° (lit³. 66°), (E) β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-37° (lit⁹. 136-37°); acetate, 125-26° (lit⁹. 126-27°); benzoate, m.p. 143-44° (lit⁹. 144°), (F) β -amyrin, m.p. 196-97° (lit¹⁰. 197-5°); acetate, m.p. 237° (lit¹¹. 238-39°), benzoate, m.p. 228° (lit¹¹. 229-30°).

Heart-Wood: The chipped heart-wood (3 kg) was exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and then with chloroform. The combined extract (34 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh) and eluted with the solvents of increasing polarity.

The following compounds were obtained, (G) n-octacosanol, m.p. 85° (lit¹². 83-4°); acetate m.p. 65° (lit¹². 65-8°), (H) 3-acetyl- β -sitosterol, m.p.